

Enter the Stack

Viable Systems Design for a New Era of Collective Intelligences

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ABSTRACT

As holistic views of systems design gain ground, the question of how we might turn the “accidental megastructure” [1] of existing infrastructure stacks into consciously designed collective intelligence architectures has emerged as a key challenge for those engaged in designing cooperative and sharing economies. If we are aiming at a “technological sovereignty” facilitated by cooperative approaches, future ecosystems for products and services must be based on alternative technology stacks. That is why we want to enter the stack - and add stack design to the conversation around cooperative and sharing economies.

CCS CONCEPTS

- Human-centered computing > Interaction design > **Interaction design theory, concepts and paradigms**
- Human-centered computing > Collaborative and social computing > Collaborative and social computing theory, concepts and paradigms > **Computer supported cooperative work**
- Human-centered computing > Collaborative and social computing > **Collaborative and social computing theory, concepts and paradigms**

KEYWORDS

collective intelligence design, stack design, anticipatory systems

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1. Different Stories

Adopting the principle that technology stacks are in principle subject to co-design, this workshop contribution showcases a series of complementary co-design processes to explore how we might best facilitate such a conversation. The workshop does not, however, assume a comprehensive understanding of data governance approaches. It begins with a much simpler idea - the search for a narrative (with a wide range of characters and multiple conflicting plots) that might be able to frame a cross-sectoral systems design conversation in which all workshop participants see a role for themselves.

2. Questions of Value

Such alternative stacks must be capable of sustaining an expanding spectrum of value-creating activities and relations - the sharing economy and the return of “public value” (cf. the EU’s recent commitment to “mission-oriented” research and innovation) are evidence of a broader transformation of value and the markets designed to facilitate the generation and distribution of such value. These developments are also indicative of a fundamental shift in how we comprehend, approach, and ultimately govern innovation - we know now that even technological innovation is never simply “technological” but in fact depends on a wide array of other less visible (cultural, political, social) innovations. To enable future and emerging technologies, the workshop aims to bring these other forms of innovation into view. If Europe intends to benefit from the emergence of new forms of (public) value, it must embrace a more holistic view of how such value is generated [2]. The idea of a collective intelligence design stack aims to offer such a view.

3. Shifting Perspectives

We realize that “stack design” is an abstract design proposition. Defined as “the set of technologies an organization uses to build a web or mobile application ... a combination of programming languages, frameworks, libraries, patterns, servers, UI/UX solutions, software, and tools used by its developers”, the view of the tech stack we are emphasizing here is not primarily technical.¹ A quick look at the stacks used by key players in and across the platform economy suggests that these modularized systems have more in common than their fierce competition for users might suggest - which is the main shift in perspectives we are proposing: a different view of the platform economy. There is more than one view, and rather than repeat the usual invocations of global brands (and their market power), we want to shift the focus of our conversation to the stacks that sustain the power of these actors - a first step toward a more comprehensive understanding of the relational infrastructures behind data-driven societies. And toward a different way of thinking about the design of (fairer) markets for a more cooperative platform economy.

4. Use Cases

The following use cases offer different points of entry and reference into the “stack design” conversation we aim to facilitate through the workshop. Before we engage with tech stacks and zero in on necessarily intricate details (which comes with the need to engage in data space design) we would like to survey some of the dynamic developments across the field of cooperative economies. Highlighting a different context and a different set of (collective) actors, each of these holds significant lessons for future design efforts and is meant to elicit additional examples from workshop participants.

3.1 Streamr

Context: Ethical monetization of data and automated creation of data unions.

Relevance: The team of Streamr, “the missing real time data protocol for the decentralized web”², has made the case that it is through the creation of “data unions” [3] that we will be able to create an alternative data ecosystem. Swash is one of the first use cases demonstrating the data union principle.³

3.2 Up&Go

Context: Collective governance challenges and global adaptation.

Relevance: Governance and collective decision making processes require innovation in platform coops. The best practices are less standardized compared to hierarchical start-ups. Up&Go has faced this challenge quite a bit. Scaling up and expanding to other regions/cultures also comes with its own set of challenges without the traditional venture capital ecosystem, despite interest globally from organizations like SEWA.⁴ A platform cooperatives incubator that is currently being created provides additional ecosystemic perspectives.⁵

3.3 CoopCycle

Context: Open source licensing and autonomous cross-cultural adaptation.

Relevance: Open source code with autonomous global collectives shows how scaling is easier without a central authority, enabling independence and decision-making authority to individual collectives but there's a need for support and innovation to enable the creation of sustainable local business models.⁶

3.4 resonate

Context: Cooperative streaming service owned by artists and listeners.

¹ <https://stackshare.io>

² <https://streamr.network>

³ <https://swash.io>

⁴ <http://www.sewa.org>

⁵ <https://www.incubator.coop>

⁶ <https://coopcycle.org>

Relevance: A co-creation effort to build a grassroots-driven (music) streaming infrastructure. Complex story involving innovative-but-ultimately-unsuccessful efforts to mobilize new (token-based) forms of VC from within the blockchain ecosystem.⁷

3.5 Platform Coops Germany

Context: Regionalization of the platform cooperativism approach.

Relevance: Process use case in “translating” a global approach to organizational development by integrating regional cultures and traditions of cooperation (here, the rather conservative tradition of German cooperativism) with a platform design agenda.⁸

3.6 HEALTH-AI Saar

Context: Integration of “cooperative data governance” in regional innovation framework.

Relevance: Regional dynamic around health-and-ai innovation, a key cross-sectoral dynamic of ai-driven neo-industrial development. Lots of implications for other areas of “smart” industrialization and the need to carefully link data space design strategies with the technological sovereignty agenda. Linkages to the cross-continental effort to establish a federated data infrastructure.⁹ Includes an effort to design a “sovereign cloud stack”, one of the first projects supported by the new *Federal Agency for Disruptive Innovation* (itself an example of the difficulty to define alternative institutional paths to innovation).¹⁰

3.7 s:coop

Context: Cooperative driven by art and design students to create an alternative to individualist start-up culture.¹¹

Relevance: Effort to transform from below existing (technology-centric) innovation narratives to address commons-oriented ideation and value creation and bring existing dynamics around peer-to-peer cultures into a regional innovation context.

5. Feeding Forward

Exemplifying a new generation of socio-technical systems, semi-automated decision making is on the rise, with capacities for data analysis and prediction that far exceed the powers of earlier generations of expert systems that simply offered static contextualizations for individual decisions. While data ethics strategies affirm the centrality of the human as “decision-maker of last resort”, these systems (applied cross-sectorally, including automotive, banking / finance, health, human resources) effectively confront us with a sober truth: a hybrid system in which machines will propose and ultimately make better decisions. If we want to resolve this dilemma - that ethics place the human in command, while technological innovation improves the quality of (soon) autonomous assistive systems - we must create cooperative decision systems that offer dynamic recontextualisation and design a co-agency model that can comprehend the hybridization of human and machinic agency. We believe that we need to safeguard not only our individual human agency but our ability to co-exist in a new generation of collective intelligences that radically alter our understanding of the ways in which humans and machines collaborate. Building a “stack design” conversations is one way to do that - stressing our embeddedness in socio-technical systems designed to amplify our collective agency and open up new practices of co-creation.

6. Shaping a New Experience

The workshop brings together participants with different perspectives in the ecosystem, including cooperative changemakers, technologists, design thinkers and policy makers. The hands-on activity

⁷ <https://resonate.is>

⁸ <https://platformcoop.de>

⁹ <https://www.data-infrastructure.eu>

¹⁰ <http://scs.community>

¹¹ <https://scoop.vision>

analyzing these cases enables participants to rethink their personal relationship and agency in the data-driven systems around them. The intention is to enable self-realization of the underlying convergent story. Through this, the workshop can lay the foundation and provide a pathway to build longer term collaborations collectively designing a more ethical stack for the platform economy.

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Many of these ideas have been co-developed by members of **anticipate** - a collective intelligence design research network (www.anticipate.network). The network's principles of engagement are: **1. Explore Impact.** Rather than solely focusing on a single technology (such as ai) as field of applied innovation, the network makes the question of collective intelligence the focus of multidisciplinary inquiry and experiment. This allows us to approach, explore and comprehend the wide-ranging implications and possible impact of machinic intelligences without locking us into the dynamics of technological development. **2. Imagine Innovation.** New imaginaries, new narratives, new horizons - if we are to anticipate worlds in which human and non-human actors become part of collective intelligences, we will need all of these. In imagining alternative futures, the network widens the space of innovation. This goes both ways, as we also need to innovate imagination. New technologies change the way we can arrive at concepts, tell stories, foresee futures. This opens up new problem spaces and calls for new conceptual blueprints to ultimately create new instruments for the organization of change. **3. Co-Create Discourses.** We can only find the new if we have a language that allows room for the unknown. Otherwise we may not be able to name the new when we encounter it - or miss it altogether. The network critically assesses the terms we have come to use to talk about the new - and creates new terms whenever we think existing terms won't do. The co-creation of new languages is one way to anchor technology design in a broader and more holistic conversation about how we want to live and work. **4. Make Worlds.** The distinctions we have established in education and research have served us only so well in building new alliances. Rather than struggling to re-connect what we have come to accept as always already separate - IT, SSH, Arts and Culture - we begin with a multi- and even non-disciplinary view of the systems and worlds of which we are a part. In the context of ecological crisis, we need to have a better sense of how the world exists - its interdependencies, its timescales, . If technology is to play a role in addressing this crisis, we need a way of speaking about worldmaking that acknowledges that technologies can play multiple roles, and that our ways of exploring impact must acknowledge the complexity of technological agency. **5. Contextualize Agency.** The conditions of change frame our agency - as they change, so do our options for individual and collective action. Awareness of contexts directly translates into new possibilities for action. We need to rethink how we can explore anticipatory assumptions, harness structures for mutual learning to meet these challenges. By collaborating with a wide range of actors, we can devise blended skillsets and clusters of competences to properly assess, scope and tackle more complex and chaotic problems. Such participatory futures will not only provide strategic vision, build capacity and guarantee impact, but also generate new concepts and instruments.

REFERENCES

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